

Use cases for Data Apps and Data Pipelines

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Executive Summary

This deliverable outlines the use cases and data-analytics components that form the foundation of the 3PhaseInsight project's approach to improving low-voltage grid awareness through three-phase smart-meter data. The project addresses a core challenge faced by Distribution System Operators (DSOs) and other stakeholders, particularly in limited visibility into per-phase loading, phase-connection accuracy, and emerging electrification patterns at the customer level. The realised benefits are also relevant to electricians and installers who work directly on phase connections and attend to customer issues. These gaps limit efficient planning, slow connection processes, and increase the risk of overloads and imbalance. Leveraging the unique three-phase smart-meter dataset made available through the project, a structured set of Data Apps has been defined to extract actionable insights that DSOs can operationalise.

The identified Data Apps cover data preparation, topology refinement, imbalance analysis, device detection, loading assessment, and harmonic-related diagnostics. Together, they form a modular analytics toolbox that can be flexibly composed into Data Pipelines supporting specific operational and planning needs. Each app is designed to serve a clearly defined purpose, such as refining meter-to-feeder connectivity, identifying heat pumps or EV chargers, or screening phase imbalance, while relying on consistent inputs from the shared data processing foundation. These components are important building blocks for downstream services, ensuring that later steps operate on corrected, reliable, and interpretable per-phase information.

Building on these capabilities, several potential high-value use cases have been defined as services for DSO operations, planning, and stakeholder engagement. These include a Phase Connection Assistant for electricians; Automated detection of smart-meter connection issues; Feeder-level imbalance screening; Customer issue diagnosis; Fuse-loading notifications; Per-phase hosting-capacity assessments. Each use case is motivated by sound operational needs and has the potential to support better decision-making through insights derived from the Data Apps. The services illustrate how per-phase analytics can unlock new forms of low voltage awareness, thereby improving customer service and reducing conservatism in grid planning through more granular and trustworthy data.

Together, the Data Apps and associated use cases provide a blueprint for how DSOs can leverage large-scale three-phase smart-meter data within a repeatable, open, and scalable pipeline architecture (which will be described further in Deliverable D2.2 [1]).

This deliverable provides the conceptual foundation for these solutions, describing what they do, whom they serve, and why they matter while deferring technical implementation details to later project stages.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Project background

The rapid electrification of the grid is placing more pressure on distribution networks, where increasing numbers of heat pumps, electric vehicles (EVs), and other power electronic devices introduce additional loads and often phase imbalance. At the same time, Danish distribution system operators (DSOs) generally lack detailed observability of low-voltage (LV) grids: topology records might have errors, phase-connection information is often dependent on the communication form of the meters and missing for some meters, and power quality monitoring is limited or absent at secondary substations. This lack of granular, per-phase visibility forces DSOs to rely on conservative planning assumptions, leading to unnecessary capacity buffers, delayed customer connections, and costly reinforcement measures that slow down the green transition.

Motivated by these challenges, the 3PhaseInsight project unlocks the value of per-phase smart-meter measurements by developing advanced analytics and scalable data-processing pipelines. The platform validates on a dataset of around 100,000 customers provided by Radius, a leading DSO in Denmark, demonstrating real-world performance at scale and establishing a proven foundation for broader deployment. The central idea is that modern smart meters can provide per-phase voltage, power, and harmonic information at a granularity that enables a new level of LV situational awareness. The platform delivers actionable insights through state-of-the-art data-driven and machine-learning algorithms, directly supporting more efficient operation, planning, and stakeholder-level data sharing.

The platform delivers a suite of modular Data Applications including per-phase topology correction, imbalance screening, harmonic analysis, and detection of significant electrification loads, such as heat pumps and EV chargers. These analytics are integrated into an open-source, cloud-deployable data-pipeline framework that supports scalable execution, modular workflow composition, and interoperability with DSO environments. By combining improved LV observability with replicable digital tools, the platform enables DSOs to target interventions more precisely, design new customer-facing services, and scale analytics capability across the sector as the electrification challenge grows.

1.2 Scope of the document

This document defines the use cases and Data Applications that form the analytical foundation of the 3PhaseInsight platform. It describes what each component does, whom it serves, and how it connects to broader DSO operational and planning needs. Technical implementation details, algorithmic approaches, and validation results are addressed in subsequent deliverables, particularly D3.1 [2] and D3.2 [3]. Together, these documents provide a complete blueprint for deploying per-phase smart-meter analytics at scale across LV networks.

2 Services and Data Applications

This section introduces the services that could potentially be enabled by the platform, followed by the underlying data applications that support them. The intention is to provide a clear bridge between technical implementations (e.g., repositories and algorithms) and practical value delivered to end users across different DSO contexts.

Services represent user-facing functionalities that support operational, planning, and customer-interaction workflows. They are defined independently of specific datasets or implementations, allowing them to be adapted to different grid environments and data availability conditions. *Data applications* (*data apps*) are modular analytical components that process measurement data and grid-topology information to generate intermediate insights. These components can be combined into data pipelines that enable one or more services.

A single service may rely on multiple data apps, and conversely, a data app may support multiple services. This modular structure enables flexibility, scalability, and reuse across different DSOs and future scenarios. An overview of the relationship between services, data pipelines, and data applications is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Conceptual framing of the terminology used to describe the 3PhaseInsight platform requirements. A *solution* implemented on the 3PhaseInsight *platform* will deliver a *service* to a user, where the service is composed of a user interface (*UI*) and a *data pipeline* which in turn is composed of a combination of *data apps*.

2.1 Potential services

The 3PhaseInsight platform could deliver a portfolio of services that address operational, planning, and customer-facing challenges faced by DSOs today. Each potential service is designed to be actionable and immediately relevant to specific stakeholder workflows by translating per-phase smart-meter intelligence into concrete decisions and measurable outcomes. Together, they could represent an overview for DSOs considering to fully exploit their smart-meter infrastructure to modernise their LV grid operations. Table 1 provides an overview of the identified services, their descriptions, and the stakeholder groups they target. The description of services is presented in the following subsections in

more detail.

Table 1: Overview of 3PhaseInsight services, descriptions, and targeted users.

Service	Description	Targeted User
Phase Connection Assistant	Recommends the optimal phase for connecting new single-phase devices to reduce imbalance and improve hosting capacity.	Electrician / DSO
Smart Meter Connection Issue Report	Combines phase mapping and smart meter classification to identify phase twists, doubled-phase connections, and incorrect feeder or transformer associations.	DSO
Phase Imbalance Screening	Identifies and ranks feeders with the most severe or persistent phase imbalance, supporting prioritised operational response.	DSO
Per-feeder Imbalance Assessment	Characterises imbalance at substation, feeder, or cabinet level to assess severity and duration, and supports root-cause analysis.	DSO
Phase Imbalance Mitigation	Categorises imbalance issues and suggests balancing actions per feeder or sub-grid node to accommodate additional loads or mitigate overloads.	DSO
Per-phase Load Profile Generation	generates representative per-phase load profile ensembles for selected load types and aggregation levels for use in planning studies.	DSO
Customer Issue Diagnosis and Reporting	Uses device detection modules (HP, EV, PV, battery) and power-quality indicators to diagnose customer-specific issues such as fuse trips or harmonics.	DSO
Customer Fuse Loading Assistant	Detects and notifies customers or service providers about recurring high fuse loading, encouraging preventive action before outages occur.	Customer
Residential Load Disaggregation	Estimates how much of a customer's consumption is attributable to different appliance types to improve energy awareness.	Customer
Phase-Aware Smart Charging	Adapts EV charging behaviour based on local per-phase conditions to reduce peak loading and improve balance.	EVSE Supplier
Delivery Point Hosting Capacity Information	Provides hosting capacity information at individual delivery points, relevant for apartment buildings and ownership associations.	Developer
Per-phase Hosting Capacity Analysis	Derives per-phase hosting capacity assessments from smart meter data using duration-curve-based methods to support connection decisions.	Customer / Energy Communities

2.1.1 Phase Connection Assistant

This service supports electricians and DSOs in making informed decisions about how to connect new single-phase devices to the most suitable phase in the low-voltage grid.

Actors: Electricians and DSO planners

Action: Determine the most appropriate phase for connecting a new single-phase device such as a heat pump, EV charger, or other significant load.

Steps:

Electrician:

1. Selects the installation point;
2. Reviews phase recommendations;
3. Chooses the recommended phase for connection.

DSO planner:

- Reviews guidance outputs and provides phase instructions to installers.

Goal:

To reduce phase imbalance, prevent unnecessary overloading of weak phases, and improve hosting capacity in areas with growing electrification. The service enables DSOs to offer clear, data-supported guidance, improving installation quality and system performance.

2.1.2 Smart Meter Connection Issue Report

This service provides DSOs with an overview of problematic meter connections, including phase twists, doubled-phase connections, and incorrect feeder or transformer associations. It helps improve the accuracy of LV grid models, which is essential for planning and understanding true loading conditions.

Actors: DSO asset/data teams, planning engineers, and operational staff.

Action: Identify and list incorrect or inconsistent smart-meter connections.

Steps: *DSO asset-data team:* (1) Selects the area or group of meters to review; (2) inspects the list of meters with suspected connection issues.

DSO planning engineer: (3) Reviews flagged inconsistencies and evaluates their relevance for planning models.

DSO operational engineer: (4) Decides whether field verification or corrective action is required.

Goal: Improve data quality and reduce manual verification efforts.

2.1.3 Phase Imbalance Screening

This service identifies, ranks, and visualises feeders or line sections experiencing persistent or severe phase imbalance. It helps DSOs focus operational or mitigation efforts on the areas with the greatest benefit.

Actors: DSO planning and operations teams.

Action: Screen the LV grid to find feeders with the worst imbalance.

Steps: *DSO planning/operation team:* (1) Selects feeders or regions to screen; (2) reviews the imbalance overview; (3) examines the ranked list of affected feeders; (4) selects feeders needing further action.

Goal: Support targeted mitigation and improve LV performance.

2.1.4 Per-unit Imbalance Assessment

This service allows DSOs to identify imbalance characteristics on a subnet (substation, feeder, cabinet) and understand severity or duration, eventually tracking root causes.

Actors: DSO planning and operational teams.

Action: Assess imbalance patterns on feeder or substation levels.

Steps: *DSO operations/planning:* (1) Selects the feeder or substation; (2) reviews feeder imbalance characteristics; (3) identifies locations with persistent issues; (4) selects points for deeper investigation.

Goal: Characterise imbalance and support root-cause analysis.

2.1.5 Phase Imbalance Mitigation

This service categorises imbalance issues and suggests potential balancing actions per feeder or sub-grid node to accommodate additional loads or mitigate overloads.

Actors: DSO operations teams.

Action: Recommend corrective balancing actions.

Steps: *DSO operations:* (1) Reviews feeders with imbalance issues; (2) examines suggested mitigation actions; (3) selects feasible actions; (4) schedules or dispatches re-phasing or operational adjustments.

Goal: Reduce losses and avoid overload situations.

2.1.6 Per-phase Load Profile Generation

This service generates typical load profiles based on selected load types and aggregation levels, producing ensembles rather than individual profiles.

Actors: DSO analysts, planners, and researchers.

Action: Generate representative per-phase load profiles.

Steps: *Analyst/planner:* (1) Selects the load group or category; (2) chooses the aggregation level/category; (3) reviews the generated profiles; (4) exports or applies them in planning studies.

Goal: Support planning studies and modelling.

2.1.7 Customer Issue Diagnosis and Reporting

This service translates analytical results into customer-oriented insights to explain issues such as frequent fuse trips, local phase imbalance, or recurring power-quality anomalies. It helps DSOs reduce complaint-driven investigations and improve customer interaction.

Actors: DSO customer-service teams and field technicians.

Action: Diagnose customer-specific technical issues and communicate findings.

Steps: *Customer service:* (1) Opens the customer case; (2) reviews automatic diagnostic indicators; (3) communicates findings to the customer.

Technician: (4) Receives the issue summary; (5) performs targeted on-site checks if needed. **Goal:** Reduce troubleshooting time and improve customer experience.

2.1.8 Customer Fuse Loading Assistant

The service notifies customers or service providers when their fuses experience recurring high loading, encouraging preventive action before outages occur.

Actors: Customers, electricians, and customer-service providers.

Action: Detect and warn about recurring high fuse loading.

Steps: *Customer:* (1) Receives a fuse-overload alert; (2) checks when and how often overload occurs; (3) contacts an electrician or adjusts usage.

Electrician: (4) Reviews the overload report; (5) recommends or performs corrective installation changes.

Goal: Prevent fuse trips and reduce equipment stress.

2.1.9 Residential load disaggregation

This service estimates how much of a customer's consumption is associated with different equipment types.

Actors: Customers, energy-service providers.

Action: Break down residential consumption by appliance type.

Steps: *Customer:* (1) Selects their meter or home; (2) views estimated appliance-level consumption; (3) identifies main consumption drivers.

Energy adviser: (4) Interprets results; (5) proposes behavioural or efficiency measures.

Goal: Improve energy awareness and efficiency insights.

2.1.10 Phase-Aware Smart charging

This service adapts EV charging based on local phase conditions.

Actors: EVSE suppliers, DSOs.

Action: Adjust EV charging behaviour using phase information.

Steps: *EVSE operator:* (1) Checks phase conditions; (2) applies recommended charging adjustments; (3) monitors charging progress; (4) adapts charging as conditions change.

DSO: (5) Provides phase-related signals to the operator.

Goal: Reduce peak loading and improve balance.

2.1.11 Delivery point hosting capacity information

This service provides hosting capacity information at individual delivery points, relevant for apartment buildings or ownership associations.

Actors: Developers, building owners, energy communities.

Action: Access hosting capacity levels for a specific connection point.

Steps: *User (building owner/developer/community):* (1) Selects the delivery point; (2) reviews per-phase hosting capacity; (3) determines if a new load/DER can be added; (4) integrates this information into planning decisions.

Goal: Enable informed investment and connection planning.

2.1.12 Per-phase Hosting Capacity Analysis

This service provides DSOs with insight into additional load or DER capacity that can be connected per phase without violating operational limits. It accounts for unbalanced loading, which often governs LV planning decisions.

Actors: DSO planners and connection-approval teams.

Action: Estimate per-phase hosting capacity at feeders or sections.

Steps: *DSO planner:* (1) Selects the delivery point or feeder; (2) reviews per-phase hosting capacity; (3) checks feasibility of adding new load/DER; (4) approves or denies the connection request.

Goal: Enable faster connection decisions and maintain system integrity.

2.2 Data Applications

The data applications, from hereon called data apps, are considered analytical and software building blocks, each defined with a specific analytical purpose, associated inputs and outputs. data pipelines and services will be composed of data apps as building blocks.

The following subsections each describe a data app in detail, covering its purpose, inputs, outputs, and role in the analytics pipeline.

2.2.1 Data Extractor

Purpose: The Data Extractor provides the foundational data-handling capabilities required by all other data applications. It loads raw smart-meter time-series data and grid-topology information and transforms them into consistent, analysis-ready formats.

Inputs: Raw smart-meter measurement files and topology datasets describing meter–cabinet–feeder–transformer relationships.

Outputs: Standardised datasets (e.g. Parquet time-series files) and structured topology mappings, provided at different processing stages (e.g. raw, cleaned, and cleaned-and-corrected data) for reuse across downstream applications.

Role in the pipeline: By ensuring consistent data formats and scalable access to topology mappings, the Data Extractor enables reliable and efficient downstream analytics while minimising duplication.

2.2.2 Smart Meter Classifier

Purpose: The Smart Meter Classifier characterises and classifies smart meters based on data availability, data quality, statistical properties, detected connection errors, and the completeness of phase connections.

Inputs: Per-phase smart-meter time-series data and topology metadata provided by the Data Extractor (2.2.1).

Outputs: Classification labels and summary statistics describing meter data quality, connectivity status, and reliability for further analysis.

Role in the pipeline: The Smart Meter Classifier improves trust in downstream analytics by identifying reliable meters and flagging problematic data or connections. Its outputs support subsequent data apps, including the Smart Meter Phase Mapper, Data Corrector, and other analytics that depend on validated and well-characterised input data.

2.2.3 Phase Disaggregator

Purpose: The Phase Disaggregator estimates per-phase electrical quantities from aggregated or incomplete smart-meter measurements, enabling phase-resolved analysis when full three-phase data is unavailable.

Inputs: Aggregated or partially phase-resolved smart-meter time-series data, optionally supported by meter classifications from the Smart Meter Classifier (2.2.2) and topology information from the Data Extractor (2.2.1).

Outputs: Estimated per-phase load or current profiles suitable for downstream phase-dependent analytics.

Role in the pipeline: The Phase Disaggregator increases data coverage for phase-dependent data apps by providing approximate phase information where direct measurements are missing. It primarily supports exploratory analyses and downstream applications such as load disaggregation or imbalance assessment, but its use depends on methodological maturity and acceptable uncertainty levels.

2.2.4 Smart Meter Phase Mapper

Purpose: The Smart Meter Phase Mapper identifies misalignments in grid connectivity by analysing voltage-level relationships between smart meters. It applies advanced methods to detect phase twists, double-phased connections, and incorrect feeder or transformer associations.

Inputs: Per-phase voltage and current measurements, topology metadata from the Data Extractor (2.2.1), and meter classification results from the Smart Meter Classifier (2.2.2).

Outputs: Phase correction signals and refined connectivity mappings identifying misallocated meters, phase twists, and doubled-phase connections.

Role in the pipeline: The Smart Meter Phase Mapper provides corrected topology information that is essential for accurate phase-imbalance analysis, device detection, and planning. Its outputs feed directly into the Data Corrector (2.2.5) and underpin any service relying on per-phase connectivity accuracy.

2.2.5 Data Corrector

Purpose: The Data Corrector enhances the integrity of smart-meter time series by handling missing values, removing extreme outliers, and applying phase corrections derived from upstream mapping results.

Inputs: Raw or partially cleaned smart-meter time series, quality labels from the Smart Meter Classifier (2.2.2), and phase-correction mappings from the Smart Meter Phase Mapper (2.2.4).

Outputs: Corrected and validated per-phase time series suitable for reliable downstream analytics.

Role in the pipeline: By ensuring that downstream data apps operate on realistic and consistent data, the Data Corrector is especially important for applications that depend on long-term temporal behaviour, such as device detection, loading analysis, and power-quality assessment.

2.2.6 Power Flow Tool

Purpose: The Power Flow Tool computes voltage and current levels at each node of the LV grid, based on network topology and smart-meter load data.

Inputs: Corrected per-phase smart-meter time series from the Data Corrector (2.2.5) and refined topology mappings from the Smart Meter Phase Mapper (2.2.4).

Outputs: Node-level voltage and current profiles across the LV network, including estimates of loading and voltage deviation per phase.

Role in the pipeline: The Power Flow Tool translates measurement data into network-state estimates, providing the physical basis for hosting capacity assessments, imbalance analysis, and planning studies that require knowledge of actual operating conditions across the grid.

2.2.7 Phase Imbalance Profiler

Purpose: The Phase Imbalance Profiler computes and summarises phase imbalance levels — including current and voltage unbalance — at the meter, cabinet, or feeder level.

Inputs: Phase-corrected smart-meter time series and refined topology relationships from the Data Corrector (2.2.5) and Smart Meter Phase Mapper (2.2.4).

Outputs: Imbalance metrics and summaries at configurable aggregation levels, identifying locations and time periods with elevated imbalance.

Role in the pipeline: The Phase Imbalance Profiler provides the foundational imbalance characterisation used by planning and operational services. Its outputs feed the Phase Imbalance Analyser (2.2.14) and directly support services such as Phase Imbalance Screening and Per-feeder Imbalance Assessment.

2.2.8 Loading Analyser

Purpose: The Loading Analyser evaluates loading levels across LV network components, identifying critical branches, heavily loaded meters, and potential service-fuse stress.

Inputs: Phase-corrected current time series and cabinet/feeder topology mappings from the Data Corrector (2.2.5) and Smart Meter Phase Mapper (2.2.4).

Outputs: Ranked lists of critical branches and meters by loading level, including service-fuse loading profiles and overload indicators.

Role in the pipeline: The Loading Analyser supports preventive maintenance, outage-risk mitigation, and customer-level loading analysis. Its outputs are used by services such as the Customer Fuse

Loading Assistant and Customer Issue Diagnosis, and become increasingly important as electrification raises the risk of localised overloads.

2.2.9 EV Charging Identifier

Purpose: The EV Charging Identifier detects EV charging signatures in smart-meter data, allowing DSOs to quantify EV adoption and evaluate its impact on feeder performance and phase balance.

Inputs: Per-phase smart-meter time series from the Data Corrector (2.2.5), optionally supplemented by known EV load signatures or external reference datasets.

Outputs: Meter-level tags indicating the likely presence of EV charging, along with estimated charging characteristics such as power level and timing patterns.

Role in the pipeline: The EV Charging Identifier supports analytics-driven phase balancing and feeder planning by surfacing EV-driven consumption that is often absent from official records. Its outputs contribute to hosting capacity assessments, imbalance analysis, and load profile generation.

2.2.10 Heat Pump Identifier

Purpose: The Heat Pump Identifier detects electric heating and heat pump usage in smart-meter data and determines the phase to which each heat pump is connected.

Inputs: Per-phase power measurements from the Data Corrector (2.2.5), optionally supported by temperature or seasonal indicators and statistical or machine-learning models aligned with the project's documented approaches.

Outputs: Meter- and phase-level tags indicating the likely presence of heat pump usage, along with estimated load characteristics.

Role in the pipeline: The Heat Pump Identifier surfaces a key driver of phase imbalance and load growth that is frequently absent from registration databases. Its outputs support hosting capacity assessments, imbalance root-cause analysis, and phase connection guidance.

2.2.11 PV Identifier

Purpose: The PV Identifier detects export patterns consistent with rooftop photovoltaic generation, helping DSOs verify PV presence where registry information is incomplete.

Inputs: Active-power time series from the Data Corrector (2.2.5), optionally supplemented by export meter flags or known production signatures.

Outputs: Meter-level tags indicating likely PV presence, along with estimated generation characteristics such as capacity and export timing.

Role in the pipeline: The PV Identifier supports planning studies and hosting capacity evaluations by providing ground-truth estimates of local generation that registries may not capture. Its outputs feed into imbalance analysis, load profile generation, and per-phase hosting capacity assessments.

2.2.12 Battery Identifier

Purpose: The Battery Identifier infers the likely presence of behind-the-meter battery storage systems by examining charge and discharge patterns in smart-meter data.

Inputs: Per-phase smart-meter profiles from the Data Corrector (2.2.5). Ground-truth signatures are limited, making this a primarily exploratory application.

Outputs: Meter-level indicators of probable storage presence, along with estimated charge/discharge behaviour where distinguishable from normal load variation.

Role in the pipeline: The Battery Identifier is primarily relevant to researchers and DSOs exploring future flexibility scenarios. Its outputs can contribute to planning and hosting capacity assessments, though results should be interpreted with caution given the methodological challenges in distinguishing storage from ordinary consumption patterns.

2.2.13 Load Profile Generator

Purpose: The Load Profile Generator produces typical per-phase loading profiles for households or customer groups, based on specific characteristics provided as input.

Inputs: Corrected per-phase smart-meter time series from the Data Corrector (2.2.5), along with household or customer characteristics such as load type, size, or consumption category used to condition the generated profiles.

Outputs: Representative per-phase load profile ensembles reflecting the specified input characteristics, suitable for use in planning studies and modelling workflows.

Role in the pipeline: The Load Profile Generator translates measurement data into reusable, characterised loading profiles. Its outputs support services such as Per-phase Load Profile Generation and feed into hosting capacity assessments, power flow studies, and scenario analyses where measured data for specific customer types may be sparse or unavailable.

2.2.14 Phase Imbalance Analyser

Purpose: The Phase Imbalance Analyser aggregates and evaluates voltage and current imbalance at the substation bus level, flagging sections with severe or persistent imbalance across multiple feeders.

Inputs: Imbalance metrics from the Phase Imbalance Profiler (2.2.7), smart-meter data aggregated by topology level from the Smart Meter Phase Mapper (2.2.4), and substation measurements where available.

Outputs: Substation- and feeder-level imbalance summaries, ranked flags identifying the most affected sections, and indicators suitable for operational prioritisation.

Role in the pipeline: The Phase Imbalance Analyser extends the meter-level view of the Phase Imbalance Profiler to the substation level, enabling DSOs to identify systemic imbalance issues across multi-feeder substations. Its outputs directly support the Phase Imbalance Screening and Per-feeder Imbalance Assessment services.

2.2.15 THD Heatmap Generator

Purpose: The THD Heatmap Generator visualises harmonic distortion across the LV grid using per-phase metrics such as THD-U and THD-I, providing DSOs with a spatial understanding of where harmonic levels are elevated.

Inputs: THD measurements extracted from smart-meter data, combined with topology and feeder connectivity information from the Smart Meter Phase Mapper (2.2.4).

Outputs: Spatial or feeder-based heatmaps of harmonic distortion levels, highlighting areas where THD exceeds relevant thresholds and relating elevated levels to device clusters or topology constraints.

Role in the pipeline: The THD Heatmap Generator provides the spatial power-quality layer needed for compliance checks and customer-impact analysis. Its outputs support the Customer Issue Diagnosis and Reporting service and serve as a primary input to the Harmonic Distortion Source Detector (2.2.16).

2.2.16 Harmonic Distortion Source Detector

Purpose: The Harmonic Distortion Source Detector identifies likely sources of harmonic distortion by combining THD metrics, load behaviour, and feeder connectivity to pinpoint contributing customers or devices.

Inputs: Harmonic distortion data from the THD Heatmap Generator (2.2.15), per-phase load and voltage profiles from the Data Corrector (2.2.5), and topology connectivity from the Smart Meter Phase Mapper (2.2.4).

Outputs: Ranked indicators of likely harmonic contributors at the meter or feeder level, supporting targeted follow-up with customers or mitigation planning.

Role in the pipeline: The Harmonic Distortion Source Detector closes the power-quality analysis loop by moving from spatial observation to source attribution. Its outputs enable DSOs to conduct

targeted interventions, supporting the Customer Issue Diagnosis and Reporting service and informing longer-term asset management decisions.

2.3 Feasibility Ranking and Prioritization of Data Apps

Table 2 provides an overview of the data apps considered to be developed within the 3PhaseInsight platform, together with an assessment of their priority, data and methodology availability, implementation effort, and technical and academic relevance.

Each data app was assessed along five dimensions. The *priority score* (1–5) reflects how central the application is to the platform’s objectives and to the needs expressed by the DSO partner, with 5 denoting a core capability that other applications depend on. *Data availability* captures whether the input data required to build and to validate each application exists in practice. It is reported separately for development and validation (i.e. does ground-truth data to confirm the data app predictions exist), and sources, namely for Radius as a grid operator in general, and for the dataset available within the 3PhaseInsight project (cf. [4]). The entries take the values *Yes*, *Maybe*, or *No*, indicating respectively that the necessary data are available, are partially available or available under conditions, or are currently missing. *Methodology availability* indicates whether an established method exists for development (dev) and validation (val) of the data app, distinguishing applications that can reuse known techniques from those that require methodological development. *Effort* estimates the development workload as *Low*, *Medium*, or *High*, accounting for data preparation, algorithmic complexity, and integration into the platform. Finally, *relevance and value* is rated separately from a *technical* perspective, reflecting operational usefulness to the DSO, and an *academic* perspective, reflecting novelty and research contribution.

Taken together, these dimensions allow the applications to be ranked not only by their intrinsic value but also by their feasibility given the available data and methods. Applications that combine a high priority score with available data, an established methodology, and low to moderate effort were selected for early implementation, whereas those depending on missing data or on methods still to be developed were deferred or flagged for later investigation.

Table 2: Overview of data apps, along with a feasibility assessment, and relevance scores. The meaning of the columns is described in the above section.

Data App	Priority Score (1–5)	Data Availability				Methodology		Effort (Dev)	Relevance & Value	
		Development		Validation		Dev	Val		Tech.	Acad.
		Radius	3PI	Radius	3PI					
Data Extractor	5	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Low	High	Low
SM Classifier	5	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Medium	High	Low
Phase Disaggregator	3	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Medium	Medium	High
SM Phase Mapper	5	Yes	Yes	Yes	Maybe	Yes	Yes	High	High	High
Data Corrector	5	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Low	High	Low
Power Flow Tool	5	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Maybe	Medium	High	High
Phase Imbalance Profiler	5	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Medium	High	Low
Loading Analyser	4	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Low	High	Low
EV Charging Identifier	4	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Maybe	Medium	High	Medium
Heat Pump Identifier	4	No	Maybe	No	No	Yes	Maybe	High	High	High
PV Identifier	4	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Low	Low	Low
Battery Identifier	3	Maybe	Maybe	No	No	Maybe	No	Medium	Low	High
Load Profile Generator	4	No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	High	High	Medium
Phase Imbalance Analyser	4	Maybe	Maybe	No	No	Yes	Yes	Medium	High	High
THD Heatmap Generator	2	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Maybe	Medium	Medium	Low
Harmonic Distortion Source Detector	2	Maybe	Maybe	Yes	No	No	No	Medium	Low	Medium

3 Conclusions

As a condensed summary of requirements, this deliverable outlined specific services built on per-phase smart-meter data that may support DSOs and other low-voltage grid stakeholders in their practice.

Assuming a modular architecture, defining data apps as building blocks, the deliverable outlines specific functionalities required to compose the suggested services. By explicitly linking services to underlying data apps, the reported work clarified both feasible capabilities and key dependencies.

This work offers a concrete basis for implementation planning and the subsequent work, including research, algorithmic development, and analytics results, to be reported in deliverables D3.1 [2] and D3.2 [3], which will detail results and algorithms for the developed data apps.

The services implemented in an open-source platform to be reported in D4.1 [5] and observations on their insights and potential value creation will be reported in D1.2 [6].

4 References

- [1] 3PhaseInsight Consortium. Deliverable D2.2: Data infrastructure, June 2026. URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21071943>.
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